

DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNAL AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.

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Abstract. In this article, commercial banks of Uzbekistan and they contain opinions and comments on the importance of internal audit activities.

Key words. Society, banking, audit, auditing, internal audit, market relations, credit.

Along with the development of society, a number of natural, economic and humanitarian sciences have been formed, which study the causes of the events occurring in society and the changes that can be expected. At the same time, together with these sciences, the science of economics began to study the economic processes occurring in the society, analyze them, and from the creation of material benefits in the society, to study the problems related to its consumption. All over the world, people are researching to create the things they need to satisfy their needs and live their lives. Along with these researches, society also developed. At the same time, there is a desire among members of society, that is, people, groups, organizations, and countries, to achieve high income by using the resources available to them and to create a sustainable lifestyle by using the income effectively, caused an increase in economic competition between them. This competition has had its effect on the development of society and economy as an invisible force. In the end, it was realized that the state economy is developing faster through the struggle of this competition in the society.

The main goal of the economic reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan today is to establish market relations in the country's economy. The role of commercial banks in the formation of an economy based on market relations is increasing. Internal audits are important for realistic assessment of commercial banks' activities and for depositors, creditors and investors to have accurate information about banking activities. Along with the development of the society, the systems of studying the economic relations in the society, summarizing the work done, clarifying the results, estimating the opportunities

that need to be implemented, and planning the future work were formed as a necessity for the development of the society.

One of these types of activity is audit activity. It is known that audits are important for real assessment of the activity of commercial banks and for depositors, creditors and investors to have accurate information about banking activities. The main goals and tasks of the internal audit are as follows:

- a) - based on the results of the internal audit, providing the Bank Board with reliable and independent information about the real state of the bank and the exact state of the effectiveness of internal control;
- b) - evaluation and analysis of the efficiency of the internal audit system and internal audit inspection processes;
- c) - monitoring the effectiveness of administrative and operational processes in achieving the goal set before the bank's activity;
- d) - monitoring the application of the risk management process and the effectiveness of the risk assessment methodology;
- e) - monitoring the financial information system, as well as the electronic information system and electronic banking service;
- f) - monitor the reliability of accounting reports and financial reports;
- g) - monitoring the risk assessment system of bank capital;
- h) - monitoring compliance of the bank's activities with the regulatory documents of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- i) - control over the complete and timely submission of regularly submitted reports;
- j) - to study the correctness and reliability of the accounting book and financial reports;
- k) - working together with the Bank's management;
- l) - conducting or providing practical assistance in conducting special inspections according to the requirements of the Bank Board;
- m) - providing information to the Bank Council about cases of violations of the law detected during audits of the audit service^[1].

External audit of commercial banks' activities is carried out on the basis of an agreement between the bank and an independent auditing firm, and the rights and obligations of the parties are reflected in this agreement. must clearly explain the information and undertake the obligations of delivering all documents. Internal audit is carried out by the internal audit service organized

¹Qo'ldoshev Dilshod Melixo'rovovich."O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA ICHKI AUDITNING MUHIMLIGI VA AUDITOR RISKI BOSHQARISH YO'LLARI" nomli maqolasi
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in banks. Its main purpose is to identify deficiencies and problems arising in the bank's activity and to provide appropriate advice on their elimination, to show compliance with internal regulatory documents and the possibilities of determining future prospects. Internal audit activities are based on flexible audit rules, widely implemented and adapted to the units of each country, covering the management of activities of various sectors and the culture of individuals.

The internal audit system- defines the internal audit (*elements that include internal audit*), the principles of internal audit confidence and advice, as well as its level of coverage (*risks, i.e. control and personnel management*)[²] and its benefit to banking activities. The internal audit service performs the following preliminary work for the control of a particular commercial bank department: an audit work plan is drawn up; the list of auditors and the goals and tasks of the work performed by them are determined; the audit report of the previous period will be reviewed, and the implementation of the measures set for them will be reviewed[³]. An order for conducting an audit and a certificate for checking cash values are prepared. Requirements for the internal audit of commercial banks №. 405 of November 25, 2000 of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the organization and implementation of the internal audit service in commercial banks responsibilities of the employees of the internal audit service are defined in the instructions[⁴]. Also, in accordance with the above-mentioned instructions of the Central Bank, employees of the internal audit service must meet the following requirements: have higher education and relevant professional skills and qualifications related to the nature of their duties; knowledge of banking legislation and regulatory documents of the Central Bank regulating banking activities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan; good knowledge of generally accepted international accounting and auditing standards; to constantly improve their skills; they should not have restrictions when planning audit programs on the scope and duration of their tasks.

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² <https://www.sciencedirect.com>. Advances in accounting. Factors that influence the perceived use of internal audit's function work by executive management and audit committee. Mark Eulerich, Jolen Kremin and David A. Wood.

³ SH.Z.Abdullaeva. International currency-credit relations. Textbook B.m.: T.: "ECONOMY-FINANCE", 2006. -576 p.

⁴ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Auditing Activities". 2000 May 26.

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